

MORPHOLOGY OF THE STIFLE MENISCI IN DOGS: PRELIMINARY STUDY

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Introduction

In dogs, ultrasonography can be realised to assess soft tissue and bony surfaces. Little is known about ultrasonographic appearance of canine meniscal lesions and their histological appearance and signification. Meniscal lesions are common in dogs and are generally associated with rupture of the cranial cruciate ligament. The medial meniscus is more often and more severely injured than the lateral one.

Objectives

The aims of this study were to set the technique for the histological examination of the dog menisci, to describe the normal echographical and histological appearance and to present 2 pathological specimens of injured menisci.

Methods

Sound menisci were taken from the stifles of an 8 month old mixed breed dog and a 9 years old Bernese mountain dog. Two injured medial menisci were also evaluated: from a 9 years old rottweiler and a 7 years old shepherd dog.

The menisci were examined in situ and after post-mortem excision in a water bath with a linear 7.5 MHz ultrasonographic transducer. Three zones were examined: Zone 1: cranial horn, Zone 2: body of the meniscus, Zone 3: caudal horn, near the collateral ligament.

Vertical sections were made. These are plane perpendicular sections to a given horizontal plane. Two kinds of sections were tested. The isolated menisci of the 8 month old dog were put on the dissection table (horizontal plane) and cut from the cranial to the caudal horn (the sections were triangular in shape, with thin axial border and thick abaxial border), or cut into 4 quarters that were then cut tangential from the abaxial border to the axial border. Menisci of the 8 month old dog were embedded in paraffin whereas the other menisci were embedded in methyl methacrylate and cut with a vertical diamond saw. The sections were stained either with toluidine blue, PAS/ hematoxylin or safranin O.

Results and discussion

Ultrasonography

The normal menisci appeared triangular and homogeneously echogenic. The injured menisci were more heterogeneous and contained hypoechogenic areas. In horses, hypoechogenic defects were associated with fibre disruption and collapse, oedema, or degenerative processes such as fibroplasias or necrosis.

Histology

Normal menisci were more fibrous in the middle, with a regular architecture composed of collagen trabeculae in two main directions: circumferential or cranio-caudal direction and radial or abaxioaxial direction. The periphery showed more chondrocytes and more matrix organised in several layers.

In this study, hypoechoic defects or heterogeneous areas were associated with fibrillation, major degenerative changes and modification of internal architecture.